

in equation 1. The reactions may be represented as :

The formation of complex ion $(AuACl_2)^{-3}$ is further confirmed by conductometric titrations. The breaks at $m=1$ and $m=2$ in the 1 : 1 mixture and at $m=1$ and $m=3$ in 2 : 1 ligand—Au(III) solution mixture confirm the formation of complex as shown by equations given above.

The present investigation clearly reveals the formation of 1 : 1 complex in pH range 7-10.

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Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(III) Complexes of a Mixed Oxygen-Nitrogen Donor

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THE metal complexes of the tridentate O-N-N donors usually exhibit interesting magnetic, spectral and structural properties¹⁻³. The strategic disposition of the donor sites in many of such ligands forces the metal ions to dimerise or polymerise, leading to metal complexes where antiferromagnetic interaction becomes their special characteristic. In this preliminary communication, we report the ligational behaviour of benzoylhydrazone of biacetylmonoxime (LH₂) towards Co(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) ions in both its keto and enol forms.

In an alcoholic medium of pH 4-5, the ligand behaves as a tridentate neutral donor and forms

1 : 1 type Cu(II) complexes. With Ni(II) only 1 : 2 type chelates have been isolated. In the case of the Co(III) complex, the initially used Co(II) salt is found to be oxidised to Co(III) and a complex of the formula $Co(LH)_3H_2O$ is isolated. In a medium of pH 6-8, where the enol-form predominates, neutral Co(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) chelates, corresponding to a metal : ligand ratio of 1 : 1, have been synthesised in the case of Cu(II) and Ni(II) and 1 : 2 in the case of Co(III). The analytical data and room temperature magnetic moment values of the complexes are given in Table I. The room

TABLE I

Complex	Colour	Analysis %			μ_{eff} B.M. 300°K
		Metal	Nitrogen	Anion	
Co(LH) ₃ .H ₂ O	Orange	8.18 (8.31)	16.90 (17.08)	—	Dia- magnetic
Co(LH)(L)	Chocolate red	11.84 (11.92)	17.12 (17.00)	—	Dia- magnetic
Ni(LH ₂) ₂ .Cl ₂ . 2H ₂ O	Yellowish grey	9.58 (9.73)	13.80 (13.91)	11.80 (11.74)	2.98
Ni(LH ₂) ₂ .Br ₂ . 2H ₂ O	Greenish grey	8.55 (8.47)	11.98 (12.12)	22.97 (23.07)	3.00
Ni(LH ₂) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ . 2H ₂ O	Pale yellow	9.00 (8.93)	16.95 (17.05)	—	2.91
Ni(L)	Brown red	21.16 (21.23)	15.14 (15.23)	—	Dia- magnetic
Cu(LH ₂)Cl ₂ . H ₂ O	Yellowish green	16.97 (17.10)	11.45 (11.30)	19.14 (19.00)	1.77
Cu(LH ₂)(NO ₃) ₂ . H ₂ O	Ultra- marin blue	15.00 (14.96)	16.29 (16.48)	—	1.81
Cu(L)	Blackish green	22.51 (22.64)	15.00 (14.92)	—	1.00

* Figures in the parenthesis indicate the calculated values.

temperature magnetic moment of all the Cu(II) complexes of the keto form of the ligand lie within the range of 1.77-1.81 B.M. and is indicative of either a square-planar or a distorted octahedral stereochemistry⁴. For the Ni(II) complexes, the magnetic moment values lie in the range of 2.91-3.00 B.M. The Co(III) complexes of the keto and the enol forms of the ligand are diamagnetic. The Ni(II) complex of the enol form of the ligand is also diamagnetic ; whereas, the Cu(II) complex shows subnormal magnetic moment value (1.00 B.M.) at room temperature indicating a strong spin-spin interaction within this chelate molecule, probably existing in a dimeric state.

A comparison of the i.r. spectra of the ligand and the metal complexes in the keto form reveals that the broad band at 3320-3280 cm⁻¹, originally present in the ligand and assigned to the superimposed stretching vibrations of the -NH and the oxime -OH groups⁵, has not been distinguished ; instead, there appears a broad and unsymmetrical absorption band around 3500-3200 cm⁻¹, which might be due to the stretching vibration of the coordinated or lattice water molecules overlapping the -NH and -OH stretches. A striking modification observed is that, the band at 1640 cm⁻¹, assigned as

the amide I band, is always shifted to a lower frequency by 15-40 cm^{-1} in the metal complexes, indicating the participation of the C=O group in coordination. Also, a positive shift of 20-65 cm^{-1} of the N-O stretch (1015 cm^{-1} in the ligand) in the chelated species is diagnostic of the oxime nitrogen coordination⁶. The C=N (azomethine) stretching frequency at 1590 cm^{-1} in the free ligand is found to be shifted to a lower frequency by 5-15 cm^{-1} in the complexes, suggesting its involvement in coordination. Regarding the complexes of the enol form of the ligand, which do not contain any water molecule, no identifiable absorption band in the region 3600-3200 cm^{-1} are present pointing to the absence of the -OH as well as the -NH groups. The strong amide I band at 1640 cm^{-1} is absent in all these complexes indicating the enolisation of the keto group and its participation in complexation in the enolate form. The N-O stretching frequency in all the complexes of the enol form has been observed at a higher frequency than is present in the original ligand. Cryomagnetic study of the Cu(II) complex of the enol form of the ligand is in progress and will be reported in near future.

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Nickel(II) Mixed Chelates Containing Two Bidentate Monobasic Hydroxyaldehyde (or Ketone) and a Bidentate (NN) Heterocycle

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WE have recently described^{1,2} a series of pseudooctahedral nickel(II) mixed chelates containing a dibasic tridentate (ONO) Schiff base like salicylideneamino acid, one dipyriddy (or *o*-phenanthroline) and a molecule of water. The most useful method of synthesis of these mixed chelates involved a template reaction on *bis*(salicylaldehydato) dipyriddy nickel(II) and related complexes by the desired amino acids. Only a passing reference³ to *bis*(3-nitrosalicylaldehydato) dipyriddy nickel(II) is

available in the literature. We report in this note several nickel(II) mixed chelates containing two hydroxy aldehydes (or ketones) and one dipyriddy (or *o*-phenanthroline) with a fond hope that these mixed chelates may serve as useful precursors in forcing novel template reactions with chosen amines or amino acids. The following abbreviations have been used :

SalH = salicylaldehyde ; 5-Cl-salH = 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde ; 5, 6-benzosalH = 5, 6-benzosalicylaldehyde ; hacH = 2-hydroxyacetophenone ; dipy = dipyriddy and *o*-phen = *o*-phenanthroline.

Experimental

Bis(salicylaldehydato) diaquo nickel(II)⁴ and other similar complexes were synthesised by published procedures.

Bis(salicylaldehydato) dipyriddy/*o*-phenanthroline nickel(II) :

Bis(salicylaldehydato) diaquo nickel(II) (0.002 mol) in alcohol (50 ml) was allowed to reflux with the heterocyclic base (0.002 mol) for fifteen minutes. The green solution was filtered hot, concentrated to 10 ml, scratched and cooled in a refrigerator overnight. The green crystals were collected, dissolved in minimum volume of refluxing chloroform, filtered and cooled in ice. Finally the crystals were dried in air.

Bis(5-chlorosalicylaldehydato) dipyriddy/*o*-phenanthroline nickel(II) :

The chloroform solution obtained as above was concentrated to 2-3 ml. To this solution 5 ml alcohol was added with stirring and then left in a refrigerator overnight. Yellowish green crystals were collected and dried in air.

The remaining compounds were obtained by following the above procedures with or without some slight variation in the volume of solvent etc. The characterisation data are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic moments (Table 2) lie in the range 3.14-3.24 B.M. being consistent with pseudooctahedral stereochemistry⁵. Their non-electrolytic nature⁶ in methanol rules out any alternative ionic formulation such as $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal})(\text{dipy})_2]^+ [\text{Ni}(\text{sal})_3]^-$. Nujol mull spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{dipy})(\text{sal})_2]$ reveals two bands at ~ 10.2 kK (ν_1) and ~ 16.7 kK (ν_2) (Table 2). The absorption peaks are somewhat broad, thus indicating considerable distortion from octahedral geometry⁷. ν_1 and ν_2 are assigned as the transitions : ${}^3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{F})$ in O_h symmetry. ν_3 transitions could not be located with